

ENHANCING WRITING WITH CHATGPT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17836731>

Abstract. *In this paper, emphasis is put on improving writing ability of students at tertiary education with the aid of ChatGPT. The study highlights the urgent need to nurture students' writing competencies while offering practical pedagogical strategies for instructors to apply in academic settings. The writer also focuses on the discussion of advantages and disadvantages of using ChatGPT. It is discussed teachers and students' GenAI literacy need to be raised to avoid them from cheating. Some illustrations of the ways how ChatGPT is operated are provided.*

Keywords: *plagiarism, ChatGPT, writing, brainstorming, essay.*

Introduction

In contemporary society, cutting edge technologies have dramatically shaped the way teaching and learning occur. It has become common to see teachers using advanced technologies in the classroom such as projector, smart board, and other devices. ChatGPT, for example, is one of the OpenAI platforms whose induction to the academic community was an amazing breakthrough in education which has had a positive effect on education practices all around the world.

From my experience, students at educational settings use ChatGPT all the time while they are preparing assignments. It has become an inseparable part of student culture. Unfortunately, some students cannot do assignments without ChatGPT. On the one hand, it is good to use modern technologies as it offers many benefits including quick access to information, and little time to finish work. On the other hand, some learners are over reliant on online resources which make them lazy and, in most cases, lead students to cheating unintentionally.

Literature review

There are many researchers (Hong, 2023; Barrot, 2023; Javier & Moorhouse, 2024) who investigated ChatGPT and its application in teaching and learning. The findings reveal that ChatGPT can be a useful education tool for learners (Javier & Moorhouse, 2024), and it can be used as a means of communication with students. However, it is indispensable for students to acquire necessary skills to use it (Hong, 2023). Scaffolded experimental activities can support students to raise their digital literacy and, in this way, teachers can aid learners to develop and use their ChatGPT skills to produce a meaningful output (Javier & Moorhouse, 2024). The research shows that when students learn how to use ChatGPT and understand feedback, they are more likely to improve their writing (Javier & Moorhouse, 2024; Hong, 2023).

Analysis and results

In writing classes, ChatGPT can be a useful tool to brainstorm ideas for students who struggle hard to come up with ideas for their essays. In these days, learners lack creative and

critical thinking skills which are vital in the twenty first century. Ideas for speaking and writing topics can be withdrawn using AI-generated tools such as ChatGPT, Google Gemini, Claude, Perplexity AI, Poe, Writesonic, AutoGPT and others. In the time when teachers see that students cannot generate ideas for their question, the above mentioned GenAi tools can be useful. The use of the tools has both advantages and disadvantages (see Table 1).

Advantages	Disadvantages
1) Quick access to relevant response as soon as the prompt is provided	1) Learners over-rely on tools that causes lack of creativity and critical thinking
2) Constructive feedback is provided to written product	2) Unintended academic misconduct – some students do not know the ways to use them correctly and this causes some cheating
3) Students’ written products are graded based on established criteria	

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of Gen AI tools’ use

To avoid unintended student plagiarism, it is inevitable for instructors to teach their students to use ChatGPT and other related platforms because they find it norm when they copy ideas and paste them as their own. One way to do it would be to teach students how to use ChatGPT in the classroom with hands-on activities. For example, in a big screen, plagiarized and good written works can be shown and compared. The reasons why they are considered good and bad need to be explained in detail. Secondly, paraphrasing and summarizing ought to be taught followed by a lot of practice is indispensable as these skills help students avoid unintended plagiarism.

ACTIONS	EXPLANATION
Teacher gives students an essay topic and the prompts	Learners read it carefully and try to understand the topic, main areas, and use dictionary if necessary or ask a teacher for an explanation
The main topic areas are brainstormed and notes are taken	Learners use their copybooks to take notes of key points and main details for later discussion
Students are grouped to share some ideas regarding the essay question	The gathered ideas are shared in groups with other peers
As soon as brainstorming and group work speaking activities, the teacher introduces ChatGPT	ChatGPT is introduced, its features and the ways it can be incorporated into writing activity
The steps of using ChatGPT is displayed on the screen to produce a piece of writing	Students’ work are illustrated to show what needs to be avoided to prevent from unintentional cheating

Table 2 A series of actions with explanation prior to ChatGPT introduction

Here is a sample writing essay question:

“Remote work has become increasingly common in recent years. Some argue this impairs work habits generally.” To what extent do you agree or disagree?

The text below is the introduction to the essay question written by the student. Scanning the text, it can be clear that it has some questions. The teacher uses this sample introduction to teach how to use ChatGPT.

“In contemporary society, many professional workers prefer doing their job at home and companies allow their workers to stay at home and complete assignments online. I believe that this trend has negative consequences on people who tend to forget their work habits”.

The following series of actions can be undergone to teach students how to use ChatGPT:

1. First, ChatGPT will be asked to read the introduction and give feedback. Then, ChatGPT asks the student to paste an essay question and the prompt. The criteria is provided that it will focus on during the evaluation. 2. The question prompt is pasted in followed by an instant response. It says it gives feedback on writing strengths, task response and ways to improve it. 3. After sharing the introduction written by the student on the bot, detailed feedback with some suggestions for improvement are provided.

If the feedback is analyzed carefully, we experience clear and structured washback from ChatGPT. First, it is obvious to see what worked well, and then it suggests areas for improvement. From the feedback, clear guidelines can be obtained which makes teachers job much easier, and students are able to understand and apply what they learnt to improve their writing (see Figure 1 and 2). The areas such as grammar and word choice, clarity and sophistication are detailed as well as the revised version to read and compare with the original is provided.

The image shows two panels of feedback from ChatGPT. The left panel, titled 'Overall Feedback', states that the essay has good intention but needs improvement. It lists four areas: 1. Clarity and Logic (e.g., overly long sentences, illogical cause-effect), 2. Coherence and Flow (e.g., unclear topic sentences, repetitive ideas), 3. Vocabulary & Word Choice (e.g., unnatural phrases, imprecise vocabulary), and 4. Grammar & Structure (e.g., article misuse, preposition errors, word forms, lack of parallelism). The right panel, titled 'Suggested Improvements (high-level)', provides four numbered suggestions: 1. Make causes more specific (e.g., convenience culture, online shopping), 2. Offer realistic solutions (e.g., stricter regulations, incentives, awareness campaigns), 3. Improve sentence clarity by breaking long sentences, and 4. Use precise academic vocabulary (e.g., 'contributes to', 'driven by', 'exacerbates', 'implement policies').

Figure 1 and 2. Interaction between student and ChatGPT

Conclusion/recommendations

To conclude, learners have to be exposed to practice more of ChatGPT with the guidance of teachers in the classroom. Teaching students how to use it, they are not prone to cheating

unintentionally. First, teachers' technology know-how should be raised by the authorities. In this way, they can teach their students to use them appropriately to avoid plagiarism. The mutual collaboration will ensure mutual and equal benefit from education. This gives rise to well-educated young generation who are capable of producing globally recognized language output.

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